

ISic3162

I.Sicily inscription 3162

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

graffiti

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329772

1. Ρ,ΛΙΚΟΥ.

2.

Edition: PHI329773

1. ΕΚΟÇΑΜ...ΟΥ.

2.

Edition: PHI329774

1. [— —]υς Καρίωνος.

2.

Edition: PHI329775

1. ΓΑΜΙ[— —].

2.

Edition: PHI329776

1. ΙΑ[— —]ΑCΝ

2.

3. Ο

4.

5. Π.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645492

PHI 329772

PHI 329773

PHI 329774

PHI 329775

PHI 329776

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 16.0537

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 135-138

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